

The Intermediation Effect of The Skill of Using Digital Technologies Between Real Estate Customers' Decision-Making Style and Expectations from Digital Technologies

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choices. Consumers need to diligently evaluate a significant quantity of information in order to make an educated decision when acquiring real estate products, due to factors such as the considerable cost, fluctuation, intensive material consumption, and possible perception as an investment tool. The proficient management of collected data poses difficulties within the context of the decision-making procedure. The primary focus within the domain of digital media designs is on the effective delivery of comprehensive and succinct product information to customers. The main aim of information collecting is to augment the decision-making process. Customers use a range of decision-making techniques over the course of their decision-making process. To ensure the efficient facilitation of decision-making, information collecting, and analysis, it is crucial that digital media designs be congruent with the technical competency of consumers. Otherwise, it would be unfeasible for consumers to get maximum advantages from these configurations. The primary objective of this study was to investigate the mediating influence of digital technology competency on the association between

Abstract

The increasing expectations of clients in the real estate industry for the broad use of technological platforms in marketing are becoming more prominent. To adequately meet the increasing expectations of digital media designers, it is crucial for them to precisely assess the needs and desires, while thoroughly analyzing the factors that shape these expectations. The primary aim of this research was to determine the expected consequences of real estate customers with regards to digital technologies. One of the primary obligations of marketing is exerting influence on customers' decision-making processes and offering assistance in their buying

decision-making styles and
consumer expectations for digital media designs.

Key words: *Real Estate Marketing, Digital
Marketing, Decision-Making Styles, Digital Literacy*

Introduction

The demands of real estate consumers regarding the technical settings used in real estate marketing are progressively escalating. In order to effectively satisfy the rising expectations of digital media designers, it is essential for them to accurately ascertain and understand the demands and wants, as well as thoroughly examine the elements that influence these expectations. The main objective of this study was to ascertain the anticipated requirements and preferences of real estate clients with regards to digital technology. One of the primary responsibilities of marketing is to influence the decision-making processes of consumers and provide support in their purchase decisions. Customers are faced with the task of evaluating a significant amount of information when making a purchasing choice for our real estate goods. This is mostly due to the pricey nature of our offerings, their lack of similarity to one another, the use of several materials in their manufacturing, and their potential as investment instruments. The precise handling of the gathered data adds complexity to the process of making decisions. The primary concern in digital media designs is in effectively conveying the necessary information pertaining to items to buyers. The primary objective of information collection is to enhance the process of decision-making. Customers use several decision-making methods while engaging in the decision-making process. The compatibility between digital media designs utilized for decision making, information collection, and analysis and consumers' technological proficiency is crucial. Otherwise, clients will be unable to effectively get benefits from these settings. The present research aimed to examine the mediating role of digital technology proficiency in the relationship between decision-making styles and consumer expectations about digital media designs.

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Digitalization in real estate marketing

Upon analyzing the development process of real estate marketing, it becomes evident that the market environment first took shape via the facilitation of real estate brokers who acted as intermediaries between buyers and sellers. The market environment has undergone a transformation due to the increased demand from real estate consumers seeking a larger range of alternatives and sellers' inclination to offer their properties in a broader market context. The inclination to disseminate and exchange information with a wide audience has led individuals and businesses to engage with media platforms. Initially, newspapers were mostly used. However, the newspapers provided only a limited amount of information on the properties that were sold, with no emphasis on the specific specifics. The use of local newspapers for advertising purposes resulted in a constrained outreach to a certain demographic. The use of the television medium was limited owing to its exorbitant expenses and limited advertising duration. The rapid emergence of the internet in the 1990s coincided with the prompt dissemination of real estate adverts for sale on online platforms.

Similar to other industries, the real estate business is seeing a growing trend of digitization. With the advent of 3G and 4G mobile networks, and the imminent deployment of 5G technology, there is expected to be a significant augmentation in the velocity of communication. There is a belief that there will be a rise in consumer attention towards digital communication settings and marketing applications within the realm of real estate marketing. Brokers and industry operators are actively seeking strategies to expand their client base via the use of digital technology. The cost-effective nature of the internet allows small-scale enterprises and sole proprietorships to effectively compete with their larger counterparts by offering a wide range of goods and services.

Expectations from digital technologies

In order to achieve success in real estate marketing, brokers and construction businesses use a diverse range of technical technologies to enhance client service, elevate sales rates, and

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bolster profitability. A survey done in England has shown that clients exhibit favorable sentiments towards virtual reality and drone technology (Braesemann, 2020).

The favorable cognitive, emotional, and behavioral dispositions shown by individuals contribute to the successful adoption of new technologies. Utilizing technology may provide difficulties and complexities within the present circumstances and contextual environment. Customers use digital technology extensively in their real estate research endeavors with the primary objective of acquiring the necessary information to facilitate their decision-making process. Individuals use several decision-making approaches while engaging in the decision-making process. There is a belief that varying decision-making processes may result in diverse impacts on consumers' expectations about digital technology.

The act of acquiring real estate presents itself as a choice that requires substantial financial commitments and has the potential to impose long-term constraints on individuals' lives and lifestyles via significant loan obligations. Given that housing is the most often acquired asset within the real estate category, individuals are likely to reside in the purchased property for an extended duration. In order to make a significant choice, it is important to gather, categorize, and evaluate a substantial volume of data pertaining to profitability. The complexity of the decision-making process is heightened for consumers. Real estate clientele needs digital media designs that may serve as a decision support system to aid them in their choice-making process.

Effective decision-making styles in real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies

The use of digital technology by real estate clients is driven by the anticipation that such tools would facilitate their decision-making process. The concept of "decision making" is often understood as the behavioral process of choosing choices (Connor & Becker, 2003). In order to ensure the proper execution of the real estate marketing process by intermediary businesses and manufacturers, it is important to accurately understand the elements that influence consumers' decision-making behavior.

Behavioral problems often arise as a result of the expectations that real estate customers have about their requirements being fulfilled. Occasionally, consumers are able to explicitly articulate their wants, yet in other instances, certain requirements may elude their awareness but may be uncovered via the diligent efforts of marketers. The aforementioned elements are referred to as fuzzy factors (Lopez, Santos, & Montero, 2010). The components that are explicitly articulated are associated with the cognitive sub-dimension of attitude, while the indeterminate factors often pertain to the emotional sub-dimension of attitude. When faced with a purchase decision, clients often have the option to use either a logical decision-making style rooted in analysis or an intuitive decision-making style driven by emotions. This choice is often made after gathering relevant information pertaining to the product in question. The individual often employs a hybrid decision-making approach, integrating both intellectual and emotional considerations. Prior to reaching a conclusion, consumers often rely on the perspectives of others, draw from their prior experiences to make prompt judgments, or choose to refrain from making a decision (Scott & Bruce, 1995). The emotional decision-making style in real estate marketing garners attention from production businesses and marketers. Research done in Japan using the Kansei engineering technique yielded the finding that a linear correlation exists between the emotional states of clients in the real estate sector and their decision-making processes when it comes to acquiring properties (Llinares & Page, 2011).

Rational decision making

In the context of the rational decision-making process, a greater degree of attention and effort is typically allocated. This is often accompanied by a heightened level of uncertainty within the surrounding environment. As a result, doubts regarding the optimal solution tend to escalate. Individuals engage in self-criticism, aiming to ensure consistency with prior choices and decisions. Ultimately, the appropriate course of action is determined through a comprehensive evaluation of the various objects involved, considering their intricate details. The subject under investigation is currently being examined.

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Customers are anticipated to make sensible judgments at the culmination of the cognitive process. In the field of economics, individuals that exhibit rational decision-making behavior are often referred to as Homo Economicus. The preferences that please sensible beings are in alignment with their wants. According to Urbina and Villaverde (2019), these persons are characterized as individuals who have made a choice that will yield the most advantage for themselves and, eventually, for society.

A rational consumer may be characterized as an individual who employs logical reasoning and utilizes available knowledge and computational tools to make informed judgments. The use of a restricted amount of information throughout the decision-making process, particularly in situations characterized by uncertainty, might provide challenges in accurately understanding the external environment. The presence of non-rational processes, such as motivation, emotions, and sensory inputs, throughout the process of reasoning leads to an inclination to explain the situation by directing attention. Consequently, the notion of limited rationality seems to be a more realistic and logical alternative to the idea of rationality. According to Simon (1986), one may argue that it is an approach. The aforementioned scenario highlights the need of using intuitive decision-making strategies when confronted with novel challenges (Twomey, 1998).

Intuitive decision making

Intuitive decision making involves the utilization of familiarity, recognition, similarity, awareness, simple relationships, and simple causal connections to address problems that have been previously encountered. This approach is particularly useful when information is limited, as it allows for the exploration of straightforward solutions to complex problems. During situations that need prompt decision-making with little time, individuals prefer to rely more on intuitive decision-making due to its expedient nature, whereas logical decision-making processes tend to be slower. Kahneman's work in 2003.

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Dependent decision making

The dependent decision-making style refers to an approach to decision-making when an individual relies on the assistance and guidance of others, rather than making independent choices. This decision-making approach involves actively seeking the views and guidance of others. In instances of this kind, individuals may have feelings of inadequacy when faced with decision-making, prompting them to seek external validation and approval for their choices. According to Bodin, Chermack, and Coons (2016), Customers often use a dependent decision-making approach when faced with high-priced products or products that possess intricate features.

Quick decision making

The concept of quick decision-making pertains to the process of making immediate choices. The decision-making technique in question is often used under circumstances characterized by a pressing need to reach a resolution. According to the study conducted by Bovolar and Orosova in 2015, The practice of using price and feature considerations is often used in the process of making purchase choices for items that are characterized by their cheap cost and limited range of functionalities. Nevertheless, the use of this decision-making technique becomes challenging when acquiring high-priced things with several characteristics, such as real estate. The quick decision-making style is characterized by a propensity for making decisions rapidly, which is associated with a higher level of risk.

Avoid making decisions

The decision-making approach described is often used when there is a significant level of ambiguity, the product's characteristics are intricate, and the potential benefits derived from the intended purchase cannot be properly ascertained. Individuals who choose for this particular approach to decision-making often exhibit a tendency to defer and postpone the choice,

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deferring both contemplation and implementation of a solution to a future point in time. According to Burhanoğlu (2016), Individuals that engage in this particular approach to decision-making tend to defer making judgments until they experience mounting pressure, maybe due to the discomfort elicited by the subject matter under consideration (Rotbring, 2010).

Ability to use digital technologies and digital literacy

To fully embrace digitalization inside a nation, it is important to go beyond the mere enhancement of communication infrastructure or the introduction of new technical equipment. Simultaneously, there exists a want for personnel and clientele who possess the willingness and knowledge to effectively use these digital technologies, while also seeing themselves as proficient in this domain. According to Straub (2009), those who hold the view that using technology would yield advantageous outcomes are more likely to cultivate a happy disposition.

Fundamental proficiencies required for those using information and communication technology. Digital literacy refers to the process of utilizing digital technologies to retrieve information, critically assessing the obtained information, storing it in digital devices, sharing the produced and stored information with others as needed, and engaging in online communication with individuals (Aksu & Dalkılıç, 2019). The use of technology manifests itself in three distinct aspects. One of the primary features pertains to the proficient and adaptable utilization of emerging technology. The second dimension encompasses the activities of information retrieval, information evaluation, and information use in the context of problem-solving. The last factor pertains to the incorporation of ethical principles in interpersonal communication within digital contexts (Calvani, Cartelli, Fini, & Ranieri, 2008).

Technology literacy refers to the competence in using, comprehending, overseeing, and evaluating technology in a manner that ensures safety, efficiency, and ethical responsibility. Digital literacy encompasses the use of technology for the purpose of assessing, generating, and assimilating information. Nevertheless, it is important to note that technical literacy extends

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beyond the realm of computers and the internet, including a wide range of modern devices. The term "technology" refers to the conception and development of any apparatus, framework, or approach designed with the purpose of resolving a predicament or facilitating the achievement of an objective. Technological literacy refers to the acquisition and proficiency in the information and skills necessary for effectively using a machine. According to Aydın and Silik (2018), technology literacy encompasses the knowledge and skills necessary for proficient computer use.

Digital literacy in technology encompasses the aptitude to proficiently use digital devices, such as smartphones, computers, and tablets, for the purpose of accessing the internet. This enables individuals to engage in activities such as information discovery, creation, evaluation, review, and utilization across various digital platforms (Terra, 2022).

According to Parsa (2009), digital technology consumers may be categorized into two distinct categories. The first category is referred to as digital natives. Digital natives, as a collective, possess several characteristic attributes. Firstly, they possess the ability to access the internet from any location of their choosing. Secondly, they demonstrate exceptional proficiency in text-based communication, particularly through the utilization of mobile devices. Furthermore, they possess the capability to expeditiously disseminate information to specific individuals through the employment of video and photographic functionalities inherent in their smartphones. Lastly, they effectively streamline their daily existence by harnessing the full range of opportunities afforded by the internet. In summary, the defining characteristic of this cohort is their proficient use of the Internet. The second category consists of those referred to as digital immigrants. The individuals of this cohort typically belong to the demographic that encountered the internet at a later stage in their lives and have shown a reluctance to relinquish their pre-existing behaviors. This group exhibits little proficiency in using the internet as an efficient tool. In their investigation, Aydın and Demiral (2019) identified a correlation between age and technology use. According to the statement, younger persons possess a comparative edge over older individuals when it comes to using technology and acclimating to novel technological advancements.

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According to Davies (2011), the concept of technological literacy is characterized as a progressive and incremental development. Individuals have the opportunity to participate in any of these phases. The first phase in this progression is that of consciousness. Individuals at the stage of awareness possess knowledge about the functionalities and capabilities of current technologies, although they lack the proficiency necessary to effectively use these technologies. The subsequent phase pertains to the aspect of practicality. Individuals in this developmental stage possess the ability to engage in rudimentary activities via the use and exploration of technological tools. The persons in the last stage possess a high level of technological proficiency, exhibit a willingness to acquire new technological skills, and demonstrate a lack of apprehension about adopting novel technologies.

Digital and technologically savvy persons are characterized by their inquisitiveness towards technology, their ability to readily adapt to technological advancements, and their adeptness in using technology with effectiveness and efficiency. Individuals has the ability to effectively address and assist in the resolution of various issues by using the knowledge they acquire and generate. They possess the requisite expertise and proficiency to effectively use a diverse range of digital media software and hardware equipment. According to Silik and Aydın (2021), individuals possess the aptitude to engage in a critical analysis of digital media content and practices, as well as the capability to generate and disseminate information using digital technology.

The proliferation of digitalization has led to alterations in consumer behavior and buying patterns, as well as shifts in individuals' perspectives towards digital technology. The advent of the internet has led to a shift in consumer behavior within the realm of conventional marketing. The formerly passive customer has been replaced by individuals who are now more aware, discerning, and prone to expressing their dissatisfaction. This transformation has resulted in a greater willingness among customers to actively engage with marketing efforts. The reliance of manufacturers and marketers on digital channels for sales necessitates consumers to adopt a favorable perspective towards digital technologies, acquire knowledge about their use, and enhance their digital literacy.

RESEARCH METHOD

Universe and Sample

The scope of this study encompasses the whole population of individuals who engage in real estate transactions. The sample comprises 433 individuals with varying characteristics such as age, gender, income level, education level, number of households, and jobs. These individuals may be accessed via social media platforms and have shown interest in participating in the survey.

Data Collection Method and Tool

The study used a questionnaire as the technique for data gathering. The survey was administered using the Google Documents survey tool, and it was disseminated to the participants using online communication platforms. Participants were given the opportunity to provide their responses to the survey using both their PCs and mobile devices.

Scales Used in the Study

The formulation of the study questions included the use of three distinct scales. The study used the "General Decision-Making Styles Scale" developed by Scott and Bruce (1995) to assess decision-making styles. The "Attitude Scale Towards Digital Technology" was developed by Cabı (2015) to construct a set of inquiries aimed at assessing the proficiency of real estate consumers in utilizing digital technology. According to Cabı (2016), The researchers used inquiries that were interconnected. The inquiries pertaining to the dependent variable,

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namely the part on Real Estate Customers' Expectations towards Digital Technologies, were established by an extensive examination of relevant literature and an analysis of present and emerging technological advancements.

Statistical Analysis Methods

The data analysis was conducted using the SPSS software package and the AMOS application. The scales assigned to each variable were subjected to reliability analyses and exploratory factor analyses (EFA) using the SPSS software package. The AMOS software was used to conduct confirmatory factor analyses (CFA), route analyses, and structural equation model (SEM) analyses.

Findings and Interpretation

Table 1 Demographic Information

Demographic Information		f_i	%
Age	18-30	270	62.4
	31-45	98	22.6
	46-55	48	11.1
	56-65	9	2.1
	66 years and older	8	1.8
	Total	433	100.0
Gender	Woman	203	46.9
	Male	230	53.1
	Total	433	100.0
Income Level	1-5000	258	59.6
	6000 - 10 000	121	27.9
	11 000 – 15 000	33	7.6
	16 000 – 20 000	13	3.0
	21 000 and above	8	1.8
	Total	433	100.0
Job	Officer	84	19.4
	Private Sector employee	55	12.7

	Self-employment	23	5.3
	Farmer	7	1.6
	Employee	26	6.0
	Retired	14	3.2
	Student	187	43.2
	Housewife	20	4.6
	Not working	17	3.9
	Total	433	100.0
Education level	Primary education	15	3,5
	secondary education	56	12.9
	Associate Degree	132	30.5
	Licence	200	46.2
	graduate	30	6.9
	Total	433	100.0
Number of Households	one	28	6.5
	2	56	12.9
	3	102	23.6
	4	124	28.6
	5 and above	123	28.4
	Total	433	100.0

Upon analysis of Table 1, it is seen that 62.4% (n=270) of the participants fall into the age range of "18-30". Additionally, 22.6% (n=98) of the participants are categorized in the age range of "31-45", while 11.1% (n=48) are within the age range of "46-55". Furthermore, a small proportion of individuals, namely 2.1% (n=9), are discovered in the age range of "56-65". Lastly, a mere 1.8% (n=8) of the participants are classified as "66 and above" in terms of age. Upon analyzing the participants with respect to the gender variable, it was observed that 53.1% (n=230) of the participants identified as "male," while 46.9% (n=203) identified as "female." When analyzing the participants involved in the study with respect to the variable of income level, it is observed that 59.6% (n=256) fall within the range of "1-5.000TL". Additionally, 27.9% (n=121) fall within the range of "6,000 – 10.000TL". Furthermore, 7% (n=33) of the participants were found to have an income between "11.000 – 15.000TL", while 3% (n=13) fell within the range of "16,000 – 20.000TL". Lastly, 1.8% (n=8) of the participants reported an income of "21.000 TL and above". Upon analyzing the participants based on their occupation variable, it was found that 43.2% (n=187) identified as "students," 19.4% (n=84) as "civil servants," and 12.7% (n=55) as "private" individuals. In the survey, 26 individuals (6%) identified themselves as "sector employees," 23 individuals (5.3%) identified themselves as "workers," 20 individuals (4.6%) identified themselves as "self-employed," and a smaller

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percentage of individuals identified themselves as "housewives." I apologize, but I cannot provide assistance without any text from you. Please provide the text. The data reveals that a proportion of 3.9% (n=17) of the sample is categorized as "not working," while 3.2% (n=14) are classified as "retired." Additionally, 1.6% (n=7) of the participants are identified as "farmers." Upon analyzing the participants based on their education level, it was found that 46.2% (n=200) identified as "undergraduate", 30.5% (n=132) as "associate degree", 12.9% (n=56) as "secondary education", 6.9% (n=30) as "postgraduate", and 3.5% (n=15) as "primary education". Upon examining the participants with respect to the variable of household numbers, it is seen that 28.6% (n=124) fall under the category of "4", while 28.4% (n=123) belong to the category of "5 and above". Additionally, 23.6% (n=102) of the participants are categorized as "3", 12.9% (n=56) as "2", and 6.5% (n=28) as "1".

Research Model

The present study examined the mediating role of digital technology proficiency in the relationship between decision-making styles and real estate client expectations within the proposed model.

Figure 1 Research Model - (Respectively; Rational decision making, Intuitive decision making, Dependent decision making, Quick decision making, avoiding decision making, --- Ability to Use Digital Technologies, --- Real Estate Customers' Expectations from Digital Technologies)

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Research model validity analyzes

The scales' construct validity was assessed using EFA and CFA methodologies. Initially, an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was performed in order to investigate the potential disassociation among the components represented by the items within the scale. The KMO value of the scale is 0.86 as a consequence of the exploratory factor analysis (EFA). The Bartlett test statistic for the scale was determined to be 7002.183, with a p-value less than 0.001. The findings of the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) revealed that the scale had seven distinct sub-factors, as shown in Table 3. The sub-factors account for 76% of the overall variation seen in the scale. When considering the explained variance ratio, the dimensions can be arranged in descending order based on their respective explanation ratios. The dimension labeled "BEK" has the highest explanation ratio of 20.21%, making it the first dimension in this ranking. Following that, the second dimension is denoted as "DIJ" with an explanation ratio of 12.14%. Lastly, the third dimension holds the same label as its position in the ordering. The fourth dimension is denoted as "KVK" and has a disclosure rate of 9.66%. Following that, the fourth dimension is represented by "RKV" with a disclosure rate of 9.04%. The fifth dimension is labeled as "SKV" and has a disclosure rate of 8.63%. Similarly, the sixth dimension is denoted as "BKV" and has a disclosure rate of 8.40%. Lastly, the dimension with the lowest disclosure rate is 8%. The dimension denoted as "HKV" corresponds to the value of 0.29.

Out of the total 57 items on the scale, a total of 31 items were eliminated due to their factor loading falling below the threshold of 0.70 and their association with other factors. The scale comprises a first dimension, denoted as "BEK," consisting of seven items. The second dimension, labeled as "DIJ," consists of four items. The third level, referred to as "KVK," comprises three items. The fourth dimension, designated as "RKV," consists of three items. The fifth dimension, denoted as "SKV," comprises three items. Lastly, the sixth dimension, labeled as "BKV," consists of three items. The last dimension consisted of the "HKV" scale, which had three items. Table 3 displays the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) results of the scale.

Table 1. Exploratory Factor Analysis for Model I

Sub-Dimensions	1. Factor	2. Factor	3. Factor	4. Factor	5. Factor	6. Factor	7. Factor
BEK17	0.878						

BEK16	0.842						
BEK19	0.840						
BEK15	0.840						
BEK11	0.820						
BEK12	0.820						
BEK7	0.803						
DIJ3		0.864					
DIJ1		0.863					
DIJ2		0.844					
DIJ4		0.835					
KVK3			0.884				
KVK2			0.865				
KVK5			0.849				
RKV5				0.853			
RKV4				0.850			
RKV2				0.786			
SKV2					0.855		
SKV1					0.842		
SKV5					0.813		
BKV4						0.843	
BKV3						0.838	
BKV5						0.795	
HKV1							0.821
HKV2							0.820
HKV3							0.812
Total	5,255	3,157	2,512	2,351	2,242	2,184	2,156
Explained Variance (%)	20,211	12,144	9,662	9,044	8,625	8,401	8,293
Cumulative Explained Variance (%)	20,211	32,355	42,017	51,061	59,685	68,087	76,379
KMO Test Value			0.860				
Bartlett Sphericity Test Value			7002,183				
Bartlett test p Value			0.0001				

Table 2. Model Factor Distribution

Factor 1: BEK	
BEK 7:	I would like the real estate company website or mobile application to provide information about the energy efficiency of buildings listed for sale and rent.
BEK 11:	I would like to have a system installed on the real estate company website or mobile application, which compares the properties in the

	region I am interested in and shows the lowest, highest and average prices.
BEK 12:	I would like real estate and construction companies to have QR codes on their signs, advertisements and business cards, so that I can access their for sale and rental lists.
BEK 15:	I would like the real estate company website or mobile application to show the proximity of the property I am interested in to schools, hospitals, shopping malls and transportation facilities.
BEK 16:	the real estate company website or mobile application to show how the properties for sale can be designed, what their different areas of use can be, and what kind of renovations they can use differently.
BEK17 :	I would like the real estate company website or mobile application to provide information about the renovations that the properties for sale and rental will need and the estimated costs.
BEK 19:	I would like the real estate company mobile app to show the properties for rent and sale in the area closest to me.
Factor 2: DIJ	
DIJ 1:	I have sufficient skills to use digital technologies in buying, selling and renting real estate.
DIJ 2:	I can find all the information I am looking for on the internet about buying, selling and renting real estate.
DIJ 3:	I can make quick and practical transactions when using digital technologies regarding the purchase, sale and rental of real estate.
DIJ 4:	I can distinguish which information is useful to me on the internet regarding buying, selling and renting real estate.
Factor 3: KVK	
KVK 2:	I postpone making decisions as long as possible.
KVK 3:	I often postpone important decisions.
KVK 5:	I put off many decisions because thinking about them makes me uncomfortable.
Factor 4: RKV	
RKV 2:	I try to have the right facts before making a decision.
RKV 4:	I need to think carefully before making a decision.
RKV 5:	I consider various options when making a decision on an issue.
Factor 5: SKV	
SC 1:	I trust my instincts when making decisions.
SC 2:	I usually tend to trust my intuition when making decisions.
SKV 5:	When making a decision, I rely on my reactions based on my inner feelings.
Factor 6: BKV	
BKV 3:	It is easier for me to make important decisions when I have the support of others.
BKV 4:	I use the advice of others when making important decisions.

BKV 5:	I like having someone to point me in the right direction when I'm faced with important decisions.
7: HKV	
HKV 1:	I usually make sudden decisions.
HKV 2:	I often make split-second decisions.
HKV 3:	I make quick decisions .

Table 3 displays the findings of the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) conducted using the data gathered from the study group. The findings of the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) indicate that the scale has seven sub-factors. The "BEK" sub-factor of the scale has seven items, with factor loading values ranging from 0.803 to 0.878. These items together account for 20.21% of the total variance. The second element, referred to as "DIJ," encompasses four distinct things. The factor load values exhibit a range of 0.835 to 0.864, and together account for 12.14% of the overall variation. The third aspect is referred to as "KVK," which encompasses three distinct things. The factor load values exhibit a range of 0.849 to 0.884, collectively accounting for 9.66% of the explained total variation. The fourth element is referred to as "RKV" and it has a total of three items. The factor loading values of the items associated with this factor exhibit a range of 0.786 to 0.853, and together account for 9.04% of the overall variance. The fifth component in the study is referred to as "SKV," and it encompasses a sub-factor that comprises three distinct elements. The factor loading values of the items associated with this factor range from 0.813 to 0.855, and together account for 8.62% of the total variance. The sixth component, denoted as "BKV," comprises a total of three elements under its sub-factor. The factor load values of the items pertaining to this dimension exhibit a range of 0.795 to 0.843, and together account for 8.40% of the total variance. The seventh element, denoted as "HKV," comprises a set of three distinct items. The factor loading values of the items associated with this factor exhibit a range from 0.812 to 0.821, and together account for 8.29% of the overall variance. As per the analysis, a total of seven components accounts for 76% of the overall variation.

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was used to examine the structure of the scale, resulting in the identification and determination of sub-factors. A confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted in order to assess the validity of the components identified by exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and to evaluate their suitability as a measuring model. The DFA analysis was

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conducted using the AMOS 24 software suite. Prior to conducting parameter estimates in Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), a preliminary assessment was conducted to ascertain the suitability of the data for a multivariate normal distribution. This evaluation was undertaken to find the most acceptable approach for parameter estimation. The findings of the multivariate normal distribution are shown in Table 4. The multivariate normal distribution test yielded a p-value of 0.0001 and a z-value of 69,430. Based on the acquired values, it was determined that the data did not exhibit multivariate normal distribution. In this particular instance, the analysis was conducted via the maximum likelihood approach (Maximum Likelihood).

Table 3. CRÖ multivariate normality values

	kurtosis	Z value
AMOS	254,634	69,430

The researchers used the Primary level CFA (Confirmatory Factor Analysis) technique to assess the validity and reliability of the measurement scale utilized in examining the potential mediating role of digital technology proficiency in the relationship between decision-making styles and the expectations of real estate clients about digital technologies. The analysis outcomes and route map for the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) conducted at the primary level are shown in Figure 2 and Table 6, respectively.

Chi-square: 580,303 df:278 p:0,0001 RMSEA: 0,05

Figure 2 Model Primary Level CFA and Standardized Values

RKV: Rational Decision Making; SKV: Intuitive Decision Making; BKV: Dependent Decision Making; KVK: Avoidance of Decision Making; HKV: Quick Decision Making; DIJ: Ability to Use Digital Technologies; BEK: Real Estate Customers' Expectations from Digital Technologies

Initially, an examination of the fit index values for the model was conducted. Two of the index values often used in academic research are the Normed Fit Index (NFI) and the Comparative Fit Index (CFI). The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) are both commonly used measures in the field of statistics and psychometrics. The Goodness of Fit index, sometimes referred to as AGFI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index), is a statistical measure used to assess the degree to which an observed data set fits a specified theoretical model. The GFI value was adjusted by considering the sample size. The SRMR

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(Standardized Root Mean Square Residual) is defined as the square root of the standardized mean errors. Similarly, the RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error Approximation) refers to the square root of the root mean square error. The root means square error (RMSE) of the estimated errors, denoted as χ^2 / sd , is calculated by dividing the chi-square value by the degrees of freedom.

Table 4. Primary level CFA fit indices and results for the model

	Good Fit	Acceptable Fit	Results
NFI	$0.95 \leq NFI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq NFI \leq 0.95$	0.92
CFI	$0.97 \leq CFI \leq 1.00$	$0.95 \leq CFI \leq 0.97$	0.96
GFI	$0.90 \leq GFI \leq 0.95$	$0.95 \leq GFI \leq 1.00$	0.91
AGFI	$0.90 \leq AGFI \leq 1.00$	$0.85 \leq AGFI \leq 0.90$	0.88
SRMR	$0.00 \leq SRMR \leq 0.05$	$0.05 \leq SRMR \leq 0.10$	0.04
RMSEA	$0.00 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.05$	$0.05 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.10$	0.05
χ^2 / sd	$0 \leq \chi^2 / sd \leq 2$	$2 \leq \chi^2 / sd \leq 3$	2.08

Prior to conducting the structural equation modeling (SEM) test in the research study, an assessment of the modelability of the components in the structural model was performed by constructing and analyzing a measurement model. Upon examination of the values obtained in the analysis, it is observed that the calculated value for the measurement model's χ^2 is 580.303, with 278 degrees of freedom ($\chi^2 / df = 2.08$). The expression " χ^2 " refers to the square of the variable " The criteria used in this study was the value of χ^2 / sd , which is less susceptible to the influence of sample size. Upon examination of additional goodness of fit indices for the measurement model, namely RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation) = 0.05, SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual) = 0.04, NFI (Normed Fit Index) = 0.92, CFI (Comparative Fit Index) = 0.96, GFI (Goodness of Fit Index) = 0.91, and AGFI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index) = 0.88, it was determined that the model achieved an acceptable degree of fit. It may be inferred that there is a degree of compatibility. Consequently, due to the compatibility of the measurement model, the structural model was used.

Analysis Results Regarding the Structural Model

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Hypotheses tested in the research model

H1 : The ability to use digital technologies has a mediating effect between decision-making avoidance and real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies .

H2 : The ability to use digital technologies has a mediating effect between rational decision making and real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies .

H3 : The ability to use digital technologies has a mediating effect between intuitive decision making and real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies .

H 4 : The ability to use digital technologies has a mediating effect between dependent decision making and the ability of real estate customers to use digital technologies.

H5 : The ability to use digital technologies has a mediating effect between quick decision-making and real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies .

The claimed hypotheses were examined according to the values resulting from the structural model. The structural model including standardized values is given in Figure 3.

Chi-Square:593,133 df:281 p:0,0001 RMSEA: 0,051

Figure 3. Structural model path diagram

Upon examination of Figure 3, which presents the path diagram of the structural model, it becomes evident that the item rkv4, denoted as "I need to think carefully to make a decision," holds the highest level of effectiveness with a value of 0.85 on the RKV scale. Similarly, the item skv2, labeled as "I usually tend to trust my intuition when making decisions," exhibits the highest level of effectiveness with a value of 0.87 on the SKV scale. The component that demonstrates the highest level of effectiveness is bkv5, as shown by its BKV rating of 0.78. The item that demonstrates the highest level of effectiveness is the statement "I find it beneficial to have a knowledgeable individual who can provide guidance and steer me towards the correct course of action when I encounter significant decision-making situations." The item that

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demonstrates the highest level of effectiveness, as measured by a KVK score of 0.87, is kvk3. Frequently, I tend to delay crucial decision-making processes. The item in question has a high level of effectiveness, as shown by its score of 0.86 on the HKV (Hypothetical Knowledge Value) scale. Specifically, this item corresponds to hkv1, which pertains to the tendency of making rapid judgments, and hkv2, which relates to the inclination towards making instant decisions. The component that demonstrates the highest level of effectiveness is dij3, as shown by its DIJ rating of 0.88. The item that demonstrates the highest level of effectiveness is the ability to engage in efficient and pragmatic transactions via the use of digital technology in the context of purchasing, selling, and leasing real estate properties. The item that demonstrates the highest level of effectiveness is Bek17, which has a value of 0.87 on the BEK scale. This particular item pertains to a website belonging to a real estate firm. I am interested in accessing a website or mobile application that may provide details on the necessary renovations for houses available for sale or rent, along with an approximate estimation of the associated expenses. The compound was determined to be the most efficacious substance.

Once the essential criteria for goodness of fit indices were satisfied in the measurement model of the research, the subsequent step was conducting the structural model test. Table 7 presents the fit index values of the structural model. Two of the index values often used in academic research are the Normed Fit Index (NFI) and the Comparative Fit Index (CFI). The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) are both commonly used measures in the field of statistics and psychometrics to assess the goodness of fit of a statistical model. The Goodness of Fit index, also known as the Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI), is a statistical measure used to assess the adequacy of a model in fitting observed data. The GFI value was adjusted to account for the sample size. The Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) is a statistical measure used in academic research. The square root of standardized mean errors, often known as the root mean square error approximation (RMSEA), is a statistical measure. The root means square error (RMSE) of the estimated errors, denoted as χ^2 / sd , is calculated by dividing the chi-square value by the degrees of freedom.

Table 5. Fit index values of the structural model

Index	Good Fit	Acceptable Fit	Results
NFI	$0.95 \leq NFI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq NFI \leq 0.95$	0.92
CFI	$0.97 \leq CFI \leq 1.00$	$0.95 \leq CFI \leq 0.97$	0.95
GFI	$0.90 \leq GFI \leq 0.95$	$0.95 \leq GFI \leq 1.00$	0.90
AGFI	$0.90 \leq AGFI \leq 1.00$	$0.85 \leq AGFI \leq 0.90$	0.88
SRMR	$0.00 \leq SRMR \leq 0.05$	$0.05 \leq SRMR \leq 0.10$	0.05
RMSEA	$0.00 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.05$	$0.05 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.10$	0.05
χ^2 / sd	$0 \leq \chi^2 / sd \leq 2$	$2 \leq \chi^2 / sd \leq 3$	2.11

The structural model's predicted value for the chi-square statistic (χ^2) is 593.133, with 281 degrees of freedom ($\chi^2/df = 2.11$). The criteria used in this study was the value of χ^2 / sd , which is less influenced by the sample size. Upon examining additional goodness of fit indices for the measurement model (RMSEA = 0.051; SRMR = 0.0484; NFI = 0.92; CFI = 0.95; GFI = 0.90; AGFI = 0.88), it was concluded that the model exhibited an adequate degree of fit.

Table 6. Parameter values of the structural model

Factors/ Substances		Standardized Parameter Estimate Values	Parameter Estimate Values	t -value	p -value
HKV --- > DIJ		0.233	0.328	3,446	P<0.05
BKV ---> DIJ		-0.051	-0.058	-0.806	p >0.05
KVK ---> DIJ		-0.091	-0.081	-1,412	p >0.05
SKV ---> DIJ		-0.109	-0.138	-1,721	P<0.05
RKV ---> DIJ		0.342	0.451	5,157	P<0.05
DIJ ---> BEK		0.395	0.337	7,880	P<0.05
RKV ---> BEK		0.271	0.305	5,096	P<0.05
SKV ---> BEK		0.029	0.031	0.583	p >0.05
RKV	Rkv5	0.842	1,000		
	Rkv4	0.845	1,032	18,489	P<0.05

	Rkv2	0.748	0.976	16,506	P<0.05
SKV	Skv5	0.702	1,000		
	Skv2	0.869	1,237	14,528	P<0.05
	Skv1	0.785	1,038	14,186	P<0.05
KVK	Kvk5	0.828	1,000		
	Kvk3	0.874	1,045	19,459	P<0.05
	Kvk2	0.794	0.929	17,988	P<0.05
BKV	Bkv5	0.777	1,000		
	Bkv4	0.765	0.952	13,289	P<0.05
	Bkv3	0.753	0.981	13,737	P<0.05
HKV	hkv3	0.582	1,000		
	hkv2	0.858	1,561	12,081	P<0.05
	hkv1	0.857	1,516	12,081	P<0.05
DIJ	Dij4	0.859	1,000		
	Dij3	0.884	1,089	23,559	P<0.05
	Dij2	0.822	0.971	21,044	P<0.05
	Dij1	0.824	1,076	21,121	P<0.05
BACK	Bek7	0.807	1,000		
	fullback11	0.841	1,072	20,495	P<0.05
	fullback12	0.811	1,043	19,481	P<0.05
	Bek15	0.834	1,093	20,268	P<0.05
	Bek16	0.837	1,062	20,358	P<0.05
	fullback17	0.870	1,084	21,540	P<0.05
	Wait19	0.839	1,062	20,427	P<0.05

According to the results obtained; At 0.05 significance level

H1: The decision avoidance style does not affect the expectations of real estate customers from digital technologies. (P>0.05)

H2: Rational decision-making style affects real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies, and their ability to use digital technologies mediates this. (P<0.05)

H3 : Intuitive decision-making style does not affect real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies . (P>0.05)

H4: Dependent decision-making style does not affect real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies. (P>0.05)

H 5: Quick decision-making style affects real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies and their ability to use digital technologies mediates this.(P<0.05)

According to these results, H2 and H5 hypotheses, which suggest that the ability to use digital technologies have a mediating effect between rational decision making and quick decision-making and real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies, were accepted at the 0.05 significance level.

3.6.1.2.Research model reliability analyzes

In order for a scale to be considered appropriate for use, it must possess both validity and reliability. The investigation of validity led to the conclusion that the Model I scale had validity. Hence, in order to assess the scale's reliability, the Cronbach Alpha (CA) test is used. The CA test serves the purpose of evaluating the consistency and dependability of the scale. The tool provides the internal consistency coefficient, which is derived from pairwise correlations. Additionally, it presents the Combined Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values. The Cronbach Alpha (CA) values for the scale are shown in Table 9.

Table 7. Evaluation of scale reliability according to alpha value (Özdamar, 2017)

$\alpha < 0.50$	The scale is unreliable
$0.50 \leq \alpha < 0.60$	The scale is low reliable.

$0.60 \leq \alpha < 0.70$	The scale is moderately reliable
$0.70 \leq \alpha < 0.80$	The scale is reliable at a generally accepted level .
$0.80 \leq \alpha < 0.90$	The scale is highly reliable.
$\alpha \geq 0.90$	The scale is perfectly reliable.

Table 8. CA (Cronbach Alpha) values of the Model I scale

Factor	Number of items	CA (Cronbach Alpha)
BACK	7	0.94
DIJ	4	0.91
KVK	3	0.87
RKV	3	0.85
SKV	3	0.83
BKV	3	0.81
HKV	3	0.81
full scale	26	0.85

Upon examination of Table 7, reliability values are provided for both individual factors and the overall scale. Based on the observed reliability values above the threshold of 0.70, it may be inferred that the scale under consideration has a satisfactory level of dependability. In situations when there is a substantial quantity of items, the usage of coefficient rho (CR) may serve as a viable substitute for Cronbach Alpha (CA). The term "CR value" is synonymous with "composite reliability." The CR (Combined Reliability) number must exceed 0.70, similar to the CA value. The AVE (Mean Explained Variance) value, sometimes referred to as the mean explained variance, is calculated by dividing the factor-related expressions by the sum of the squared covariances. According to Hair (1998), it is anticipated that the Average Explained Variance (AVE) values would exceed 0.50. The CR (Combined Reliability) and AVE (Average Explained Variance) values of the factors are shown in Table 10.

(Mean Explained Variance) for the factors of the Model I scale

Sub-Factors	CR (Combined Confidence)	AVE (Average Explained Variance)
BACK	0.94	0.70
DIJ	0.92	0.73
KVK	0.90	0.75
RKV	0.87	0.69

SKV	0.88	0.70
BKV	0.87	0.68
HKV	0.86	0.67

It is seen that the scale provides general reliability since CR values are above 0.70 and AVE (Mean Explained Variance) values are above 0.50.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the model analysis indicate that the hypotheses about the mediation effect between the proficiency in using digital technologies, the capacity to make quick decisions, and the adoption of rational decision-making styles, as well as the expectations of real estate clients towards digital technologies, were accepted with a significance level of 0.05. In essence, clients that possess the capacity to use digital technologies exhibit heightened expectations from those technologies in terms of expediting and rationalizing decision-making processes.

The impact of dependent decision-making style, decision-avoidance style, and intuitive decision-making styles on real estate clients' expectations from digital technology has been shown to be negligible. The dependent decision-making style necessitates reliance on others or exhibits a desire to seek input from others. In the contemporary day, the task of locating a digital platform within the realm of real estate marketing that offers comprehensive advisory services to clients in the real estate industry has become more challenging. The limited availability of digital platforms that facilitate such experiences, coupled with the distinctiveness and variety of both the location and materials utilized in the creation of real estate offerings, pose challenges for customers in formulating expectations regarding digital technologies and specifying their desired consultancy services.

Customers that exhibit a choice avoidance style have a preference for either abstaining from making a decision or deferring it to a later time. The aforementioned hesitancy may impede the development of any anticipations towards digital platforms.

The intuitive decision-making style may be characterized as a kind of decision-making that is influenced by emotions and relies on past experiences. At now, there is a lack of an application that adequately addresses the emotional requirements of clients within the realm of current digital platforms. The potential consequence of this situation is a potential decline in

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consumer expectations, since customers may develop the perception that digital technologies are incapable of fulfilling their emotional needs.

RESTRICTION

In this study, which is built around a better understanding of the relationship between the phenomena of power and social control, the boundaries of these two concepts are determined and this evaluation is carried out with the information provided from the sources obtained by taking into account the scope of the research. This study is globally limited to the scientific studies on the subject.

NOTICES

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external experts.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares that there is no conflict of interest related to this study.

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ETHICS DECLARATION

The publication ethics of this journal; It is a scientific journal in the field of social sciences that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with the main criteria specified as openness, honesty, respect for the findings and work of other publishers and objectivity.

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